

Transcritical Bifurcation Proof

- **Article:** Study on Fear-Induced Group Defense and Cooperative Hunting: Bifurcation, Uncertainty, Seasonality, and Spatio-temporal Analysis in Predator-Prey System
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Our proposed system is:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dH}{dt} &= \frac{bH}{1 + \beta P} - d_1H - \frac{rH^2}{K + K_1H} - \frac{(h + \alpha P)HP}{1 + b_2H + b_3\beta H^2} \equiv F_1(H, P) = Hf_1(H, P), \quad (\text{say}) \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= \frac{e(h + \alpha P)HP}{1 + b_2H + b_3\beta H^2} - d_2P \equiv F_2(H, P) = Pf_2(H, P), \quad (\text{say})\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

Theorem 1. *At the bifurcation threshold $d_2^{[TC]} = \frac{eh\hat{a}}{1 + b_2\hat{a} + b_3\beta\hat{a}^2}$, the system (1) undergoes a transcritical bifurcation around the predator-free equilibrium point $E_a(\hat{a}, 0)$ where, $\hat{a} = \frac{K}{1 - K_1}$.*

Proof. We will use Sotomayor's theorem [Perko, 2013] to prove the presence of transcritical bifurcation in system (1). The Jacobian matrix at $E_a(\hat{a}, 0)\Big|_{d_2=d_2^{[TC]}}$ is

$$J(E_a)\Big|_{d_2=d_2^{[TC]}} = \begin{bmatrix} r - \frac{2r\hat{a}}{K + K_1\hat{a}} + \frac{r\hat{a}^2K_1}{(K_1\hat{a} + K)^2} & -\left(b\hat{a}\beta + \frac{h\hat{a}}{1 + b_2\hat{a} + b_3\beta\hat{a}^2}\right) \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = M$$

It follows that 0 is an eigenvalue of the matrix M . Thus, 0 is also an eigenvalue of M^T , and let W and Z denote the eigenvectors corresponding to 0 of the matrices M and M^T , respectively. Here, $W = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ w_1 \end{pmatrix}$,

and $Z = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$, where, $w_1 = \frac{r\left((K_1^2 - K_1)\hat{a}^2 + 2K(K_1 - 1)\hat{a} + K^2\right)(1 + b_2\hat{a} + b_3\beta\hat{a}^2)}{(K_1\hat{a} + K)^2\hat{a}(b\beta - bb_2\beta\hat{a} + bb_3\beta^2\hat{a}^2 + h)}$.

Let $\mathcal{F}(H, P) = \begin{bmatrix} F_1(H, P) \\ F_2(H, P) \end{bmatrix}$.

So the transversality conditions for transcritical bifurcation are,

$$Z^T \left[\mathcal{F}_{d_2} \left(E_a; d_2 = d_2^{[TC]} \right) \right] = 0$$

$$Z^T \left[D\mathcal{F}_{d_2} \left(E_a; d_2 = d_2^{[TC]} \right) W \right] = \frac{r\left((K_1^2 - K_1)\hat{a}^2 + 2K(K_1 - 1)\hat{a} + K^2\right)(1 + b_2\hat{a} + b_3\beta\hat{a}^2)}{(K_1\hat{a} + K)^2\hat{a}(b\beta - bb_2\beta\hat{a} + bb_3\beta^2\hat{a}^2 + h)} \neq 0$$

$$Z^T \left[D^2\mathcal{F} \left(E_a; d_1 = d_1^{[TC]} \right) (W, W) \right] = \mathcal{A} + 2 \cdot w_1 \cdot \mathcal{B} + w_1^2 \cdot \mathcal{C} \neq 0$$

where,

$$\mathcal{A} = -\frac{2e(\alpha P + h)P(b_2 + 3b_3\beta H - b_3^2\beta^2H^3)}{(1 + b_2H + b_3\beta H^2)^3}, \quad \mathcal{B} = -\frac{e(b_3\beta H^2 - 1)(2\alpha P + h)}{(1 + b_2H + b_3\beta H^2)^2}, \quad \mathcal{C} = \frac{2e\alpha H}{1 + b_2H + b_3\beta H^2} \text{ and}$$

$$\left(\frac{2e(\alpha P + h)P(b_2 + 3b_3\beta H - b_3^2\beta^2H^3)}{(1 + b_2H + b_3\beta H^2)^3} + 2 \cdot w_1 \cdot \frac{e(b_3\beta H^2 - 1)(2\alpha P + h)}{(1 + b_2H + b_3\beta H^2)^2} \right) \neq w_1^2 \cdot \frac{2e\alpha H}{1 + b_2H + b_3\beta H^2}$$

Thus, by the help of Sotomayor's theorem we can say that the system has transcritical bifurcation around $E_a(\hat{a}, 0)$ at the bifurcation threshold $d_2^{[TC]} = \frac{eh\hat{a}}{1 + b_2\hat{a} + b_3\beta\hat{a}^2}$. ■

References

Perko, L. [2013] *Differential Equations and Dynamical Systems*, Vol. 7 (Springer Science & Business Media), doi:10.1007/978-1-4613-0003-8.